

ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Inclusive Education is the modern trend aimed towards providing quality of education to the special needed children. Education of children with special needs has come a long way from integrated education to inclusive education (access to the mainstream). In spite of the support by a number of policies and programmes from time to time accelerate the pace of all the efforts made in this direction the regular school with inclusive orientation face many barriers and challenges. The Challenges are the ‘the whole idea of inclusive education is defeated on the part of teachers, parents, community and classmates. Lack of trained teachers, large class size, lack of child centered and relevant curriculum, limited appropriate teaching learning materials, teachers lack competency and will modify methodology as per the need, lack of proper infrastructure, lack of access to main stream and lack of participatory activities. There is a need to strengthen teacher’s competencies skills in inclusive education and to reform teacher training in its form and content the challenge of inequality and discrimination among students based on socioeconomic, ethnic and cultural profiles (Example: the competencies and learning outcomes achieved). The greatest challenge for the state government is the achievement accessibility inclusion and empowerment of children with special needs. The government alone cannot accomplish this task of making the “Right Real”. It can be concluded that these types of gaps can only be fulfilled with the help of collaboration to all the stake holders like University, teacher education institution etc.

Keywords: Inclusive education, barriers, challenges, mainstream.

Introduction

Education to which we generally conceive as schooling in a deliberate endeavor of the society to make necessary arrangements whereby the young budding may require various habits knowledge and attitudes necessary to meet the demands of life. Education is a process of teaching learning where a more mature person impart the necessary adequate information to a less mature to bring about modification in his behavior, so education is a goal directed activity. Education is a process

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of acquiring knowledge and changing behavior as the result of imitation, training and experience. In this sense, education is instruction which has its specific goals, planning, contents, and strategies. These goals, contents and teaching techniques are planned keeping in view the different levels of learner’s development and also their personal and educational need. Nevertheless to say the learners besides their maturity level, differ in a variety of other ways mental ability physical and emotional status interest, attitudes aptitudes and so many socio-cultural characteristics. Inclusive education is a new approach towards educating the children with disability and learning difficulties along with normal ones under the same class. It implies all learners with and without disability being able to learn together through access to common preschool schools and community of support services.

Concept of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is the principle and practice of educating all children with in a common general education setting. Inclusive education targets especially those children who are traditionally excluded from general education for the reasons of gender, geographic, remoteless, ethnicity, poverty and disability. Inclusive education is a method of creating communities school and societies free from discrimination. Inclusive education happens when children with or without disabilities participate and learn together in the same classes. Inclusive school must recognize and respond to the diverse needs of its student accommodating both different styles and rate of learning ensuring quality education to all the disabled through appropriate curricula organizational arrangements, teaching strategies, resource used. Inclusive education aimed at giving quality of education for all. Inclusive education is sensitive to the needs of every individual and is designed towards the attainment of equality, equity, quality and social justice now it is crucial that all policy makers school boards administrators guidance counsellors, teacher, parents, and students ensure inclusive practice in all aspects of educational environments. Inclusive education is about ensuring access to quality education for all students by effectively meeting their diverse needs in a way that is responsive, accepting respectful and supportive. Students participate in the education program in a common learning environment with support to diminish and remove barriers and obstacles that may lead to exclusion.

Background of the Inclusive Education

The Government of India constitute to ensuring to right of every child to basic education. The

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Government of India has created numerous policies around Special education since the country independence in 1947. One of the earliest formal initiatives undertaken by the Government of India was the integrated education for disabled children scheme of 1974 (NCERT 2011). The Kothari Commission (1966) highlights the importance of educating children with disabilities during the post-independence period. In 1980, the ministry of welfare government of India realized the crucial need of an institution to monitor and regulate the HRD programmes in the field of disability rehabilitation. The nation policy of education 1986 (NPE 1986) and the programme of action (1992) stresses the need for integrating children with special needs with other groups. The government of India implemented the District Primary education project (DPEP) in 1994-95. SarvashikshaAbhiyan (SSA) was launched to achieve the goal of universalization of elementary education in 2001. Which ensures that any child with social needs (cwsn) irrespective of the kind category and degree of disability is provided meaningful and quality education national curriculum framework (NCP 2005) has laid down a class contact of inclusive education. In 2005 the Ministry of Human Resource Development has implemented a national action plan for the inclusion in education of children and youth with disabilities. RashtriyaMadhyamikaShikshaAbhiyan (RMSA) from 2013. It is important to integrate these children into regular school to help them socialize and build confidence.

Following are the policies and legislative framework of our country for the betterment of education and inclusion:

National Education Policy (1968)

National Policy on Education (1986)

Bahrul Islam Committee (1985)

Programme of Action MHRD (1990 & 1992)

Centrally sponsored scheme of integrated scheme education for the disabled (1974)

Project Integrated education for the disabled (1987), Rehabilitation Council of India Act (1992)

Persons with Disabilities Act (1995)

District Primary Education Programme (1994)

Janshala, 1998

National Trust Act, 1999

Action plan for inclusion education of children and youth with disabilities, 2005

SarvaShikshaAbhiyan, 2001

National Policy for Persons with disabilities, 2006

Types of Disabilities

1. Visual Impairment
2. Hearing Impairment
3. Mentally retarded
4. Physically handicapped
5. Learning disabilities
6. Speech disabilities
7. Emotional disturbance leading to behavior problems

Role of Teacher in Inclusive Education

1. Identification of the children with disabilities in the classroom.
2. Referring the identified to the experts for further examination and treatment
3. Placing the children in the classroom in proper places so that they feel comfortable and are benefited by the classroom interaction.
4. Involving the children with disabilities in almost all the activities of the classroom
5. Collaborating with educational officials medical and physiological personnel social workers, parents and special teachers.
6. Accepting the children with disabilities
7. Developing positive attitude between normal and disabled children
8. Removing architectural barriers wherever possible so that children with disabilities in almost all the activities of the classroom
9. Making suitable adaptation in the curriculum transaction so that the children with disabilities learn according to their ability.
10. Preparation of teaching aids which will help the children with disabilities learn.
11. Parental guidance and counseling and public awareness program through school activities.
12. Collaborating with medical and physiological panels, social workers parents and special teachers.
13. Construction of achievement and diagnostic tool.

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14. Adaptation in evaluation for children with special needs.
15. Conducting case studies and action research related to specific problem of children with special needs.
16. True teacher can enable a disabled child to overcome his abilities and make him a productive citizen of society.
17. Providing remedial instruction to the children who require it.

The new challenges to inclusive education are to meet the need of all children with and without disabilities in the general classroom. It is not an easy process and requires a lot of struggle and commitment to overcome attitude and social barriers. One of the determinant factors refers to attitudes of the community towards persons with disabilities and inclusion. A limited understanding of the concept of disabilities and a hardened resistance to change are the major barrier in inclusive education.

1. Lack of access to the mainstream. Many schools do not show willingness to cater to the needs of their children.
2. The whole idea of inclusive education is defeated due to lack of awareness positive attitude and sensitivity on the part of teacher classmates, parents, and community and to a result these children experience discrimination.
3. Lack of trained teacher. Teacher lack competence and to modify methodology as per the need of these children.
4. Lack class size: there are normally students in a class which makes individuals and attention very difficult and teacher find it all the more difficult with children with special needs.
5. Lack of child centered and relevant curriculum. The curriculum lacks flexibility and does not provide choice to these children. The teaching-learning materials is also not appropriate for children with and without special need.
6. Lack of participatory activities: Children with special need require such learning environment in which they can learn by participating in small groups.
7. Lack of adequate equipments or adaptive communication and language tools. It makes it difficult for the teachers to function as a united classroom.
8. Lack of individual attention: Because there are varying abilities in the classroom teacher can be challenged to address individual academic need based on ability.

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9. Co-ordinatingtherapies: A special needs inclusion classroom need to be well organized and allow for student to attend therapy sessions. However this becomes a challenge in planning day today activities and keeping all students engaged and learning.
10. Economic barriers funding revising for education has always been problematic. Even if the system is well resourced overall there is almost always a feeling that resources are inadequate to meet the learner’s needs. In India the situation regarding resources is not very encouraging. There is acute shortage of finances especially to be spent on education. Some of the problems are inherently crept in the system.
11. Policies barriers. Many policy makers don’t understand or believe in inclusive education and these leaders can stonewall efforts to make school policies more inclusive. This can exclude whole group of learners from the mainstream educational system thereby preventing them from enjoying the same opportunity for education and employment afforded to traditional student.
12. Poor Organisation of the education system. Responsibility for decision tends to located at the highest level and the focus of management remains oriented towards employees complying with rules rather than ensuring quality service delivery.
13. Socio-Economic factors : Area that are traditionally poor and those with higher than average
